

LANGUAGE AND THE BENEFITS OF LEARNING OTHER LANGUAGES.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13982498>

Abstract. *In this article, it is expressed that language is the most necessary element in a person's life. How language influences culture and human life. Learning a foreign language, but at the same time it is important not to lose our native language.*

Key words: *Language, society, bilingual, culture, native language, second/foreign language.*

ЯЗЫК И ПРЕИМУЩЕСТВА ИЗУЧЕНИЯ ДРУГИХ ЯЗЫКОВ.

Аннотация. *В этой статье высказывается мнение, что язык является самым необходимым элементом в жизни человека. Как язык влияет на культуру и жизнь человека.*

Изучаем иностранный язык, но при этом важно не потерять родной язык.

Ключевые слова: *Язык, общество, двуязычный, культура, родной язык, второй/иностраннй язык.*

The most amazing and wise thing that humanity has created is language. First, humans transmit culture to other societies or eras through language. Second, use language to express your desires or intentions. Third, interpersonal relationships can be formed in the process of using language. Fourth, it functions to clarify one's thoughts or control one's actions.

All people on Earth can speak. They speak different languages, but all languages have the same task - to help people understand each other when communicating and in common work.

Undoubtedly, language occupies a special place in the life of any society. Language is an important tool for human interaction and communication. Thanks to language, we can express our thoughts in speech form. Language is a transmitter of information, thanks to which a person can share his experiences with other members of his society and pass on skills to next generations. The development of language is inextricably linked with the development of society itself. Without language, the life of people, society, the development of science, technology, and art are impossible. Learning other languages helps society establish contacts with members of other language groups, exchange knowledge and experience, which undoubtedly has a positive effect on the development of humanity as a whole. The more people speak the same language, the more society as a whole develops, since the knowledge and skills of one people can be increased by the knowledge of others. A person analyzes all the information received from other members of society, thanks to this the process of scientific knowledge of the world around him arises.

Language is a living organism that is influenced by historical, political and social changes in the life of the public. Speech, text, the whole language changes a little, which indicates a change in society. When new environmental conditions are created, new words appear, often borrowed from other languages. Research shows that the language we use changes not only the way we think, but also the way we perceive the world and how we interact with it. A study published in the journal Psychological Science describes how English and German speakers perceive and describe

their environment differently. Their speech changes depending on the language they are currently using. When speaking German, people described an action in relation to its goal. For example, "this person is walking towards that building." When they spoke English, they only mentioned the action: "this person is coming."

Learning two or more languages from an early age goes beyond just being able to communicate in a new language. It will even bring you great rewards in your life. Learning different languages helps you gain the empathy, adaptability and cultural acceptance that is truly needed in this era of globalization. Scientists have conducted experiments showing that people who know more than one language delay memory loss by several years due to the development of neural connections. When a person speaks several languages, his neural network works more intensely. In this case, the brain will be better preserved. This postpones the theoretically possible decrease in intellectual abilities, including memory loss. Learning two or more languages doesn't necessarily mean you're smarter, but speaking more than one language allows your brain to think more flexibly and makes you more adaptable. In particular, research has shown that our abilities increase as we age. Some studies have shown children that earned more than one language have greater ability to think flexibly when performing certain mental exercises. Also found that adults who are regularly bilingual and can speak both languages without any difficulty have the ability to think faster.

If technology was the most powerful weapon of the 20th century, then we can say with confidence that languages have taken this position in the 21st century. In most workplaces, language skills were the most important factor in differentiating candidates. As technological advances lead to more companies going international, they need people who speak the local language. Multilingual communication at work not only increases productivity and opens up new career opportunities, but also allows you to expand any project around the world. As noted, an indicator of high culture is knowledge foreign languages. Biographies of many historical persons, significant figures indicate that they knew several foreign languages, and used their knowledge in their activities and policies. Language learning especially important for people who want to work, live or travel in another country in the future. This will give you many benefits beyond the required skills for future success, such as empathy, adaptability and flexibility.

Over the course of our lives, we can learn new languages, which provide the opportunity to experience different cultures and can broaden our worldview. Language influences our thinking and learning process. Therefore, when a person knows more than one language, he has several pictures of the world. This means a richer life. You should learn foreign languages not because it is useful for travel, but because when you penetrate another language, you penetrate into other worlds. When you know the language of another people, you also know its culture and history.

Language and speech leads people not only to understanding in communicating with each other, but also develops art and religion. Since singing came from the tongue. Each language reflects the spiritual culture and centuries-old history of each nation. And therefore we must appreciate it, try not to litter it with profanity and parasitic words, because by doing this we are causing great harm, first of all, to the centuries-old culture of our people and our personality.

Losing cultural identity is a big disadvantage of learning a foreign language. In some cases, especially for young people, learning a second language results in neglecting their native language.

For example, you moved to another country and most of the time you have to communicate in a different language. Eventually, you may begin to lose your native language. And since language is closely tied to our cultural identity, this can lead to the feeling that you no longer have a strong connection to your home culture.

Language is not only a means of communication, it is also the historical memory of every people. In order to make a person nobody, he simply must be deprived of his native language. And subsequently he will lose not only his language but also the literary heritage, history and culture of his people, ancestors and even himself. And therefore, when invaders want to conquer a state, they first try to get rid of the state language and instead introduce another language (more precisely, the language of the invaders). We can learn about this in books about the history of the world. In order not to lose your native language, you need to take care of it, use it on a regular basis and be proud of it. Learn foreign languages but don't forget about your native one.

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